

**Career Services &
Employer Alliance**

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AI & GLOBAL BUSINESS SCHOOL CAREER EDUCATION: OPPORTUNITIES & CHALLENGES (CSEA practitioner snapshot)

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UCD Michael Smurfit Graduate Business School

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Scope and purpose

This practitioner snapshot synthesises insights from three opt-in CSEA member gatherings (EMEA conference, Global conference, and a webinar) held between April and September 2025, using a reflexive thematic approach. In total, 81 contributors from across four continents shared perspectives on AI in business school careers education via anonymous Mentimeter polling and a brainwriting exercise. It is offered as a collegial synthesis by UCD Michael Smurfit Graduate Business School to inform local interpretation, adaptation and debate.

Key opportunities (O1–O5)

- Student development & skill-building: using AI as a coaching partner to strengthen employability practice and reflective learning.
- Efficiency & administration: streamlining routine tasks to release adviser time for higher-value guidance.
- Personalisation & on-demand access: scalable, tailored support that broadens access and consistency.
- Innovation & sector intelligence: faster labour-market scanning, ideation and trend awareness.
- Employer alignment & collaboration: deeper coordination with recruiters and better alignment to hiring standards.

Key challenges (C1–C5)

- Capability gaps (staff & students): uneven AI literacy and prompting skills.
- Authenticity, humanity & learning: risks of homogenisation and over-reliance that may undermine learning.
- Professional identity & relevance:

***Career Services & Employer Alliance (CSEA)** is a global professional network for MBA/Masters in business career services professionals and the employers who hire those students. Its aim is to bring these groups together for learning, networking, and community and enable members to collaborate to support one another while developing lasting relationships that help make their job easier. (www.cseaglobal.org)

clarifying where human expertise adds distinctive value.

- Ethics & responsible use: concerns about bias, privacy, and integrity; need for clear frameworks.
- Institutional agility & pace: policy, ownership and governance lag rapid technological change.

Role Implications

Career professionals describe a shift from information provider to meaning-maker, acting as custodians of authenticity and ethics, facilitators of co-intelligence skills, aligners with employer expectations, and human connectors in increasingly digital services.

Data notes

Contributions were anonymous and reflect practitioner views at a point in time; findings are not generalisable beyond participants. Charts report totals aggregated across all sessions, using a conservative keyword scan of anonymised notes (duplicates removed; one count per note per theme). Some poll constructs (e.g., "AI literacy", "prompt writing") were self-defined by respondents. The intent is applied and forward-looking: to inform service design, team capability, and student support in an AI-enabled era.

INTRODUCTION

AI is redefining the practice of careers education in business schools. It is changing the kinds of skills students require and shaping how they prepare, position themselves with employers, and approach recruitment. Careers educators play a critical role in enabling students to navigate increasingly competitive selection processes and fast-evolving industries, ensuring support that is personalised, ethical, and aligned with contemporary employer expectations.

As a global business school, UCD Michael Smurfit Graduate Business School is a long-standing member of the CSEA. This practitioner snapshot from a member institution synthesises inputs from fellow CSEA members to examine what AI means for careers education, focusing on practical implications for service design and student support. It has been prepared in the spirit of collegiality as business schools' career services around the world grapple with what AI means for the future of work.

The report presents the perspectives of practitioners from a range of institutional contexts and illustrates how careers professionals see AI reshaping both practice and the support required by students. Students and employer perspectives are beyond the scope of the report. The findings are based on a thematic analysis of the outputs of three gatherings of CSEA members between April and September 2025, and represent the views of participants, not UCD or CSEA. The sessions were facilitated by Bernie Burke, UCD Michael Smurfit Graduate Business School and Irish Fulbright TechImpact Scholar 2025-2026.

The report provides a view of business school career education at a particular moment in time and is intended as a collaborative discussion document that may help to inform organisational planning and strategy going forward. The findings are not generalisable beyond participants.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

Careers service (vast majority) and supplier members supporting business school students participated in three one-hour dialogues (self-selected). 81 of the attendees completed the poll. No names or contact details were collected so all inputs were anonymous. Participants represented business schools across four continents.

Cohort	n	Date	Modality	Region
EMEA conference	24	Apr 8, 2025	In-person	EMEA
Global conference	21	Jun 19, 2025	In-person	Global
CSEA webinar	36	Sep 9, 2025	Virtual	Global
Total	81	—	—	—

Data sources

- (i) Mentimeter polls at session start captured self-ratings and current practice. All questions may not have been answered by participants.
- (ii) Brainwriting (rapid, individual, idea-writing exercise) captured each participant's top three opportunities and challenges on colour-coded Post-its at the in-person sessions and through Mentimeter at the webinar.

Analytical Approach (See Appendices 1-3)

Brainwriting Post-its (EMEA, Global) and Mentimeter open-text comments (Webinar) were analysed via reflexive thematic analysis (iterative coding and theme development). An audit trail was maintained; cross-cohort convergence and divergence were noted. To gauge salience, anonymised open-text was cleaned (duplicates removed) and scanned with a light keyword set.

Counts use a conservative rule: one count per note per theme, aggregated across sources, and are indicative only (face-validity). Themes are reported by salience, not prevalence, because contributions were optional and note-based, themes were non-exclusive, and no person-level denominator was available. Opportunity themes are O1–O5 and challenges C1–C5, ordered by total mentions; figures and tables follow this ordering.

Limitations

This practice-led, descriptive, time-bound snapshot is not generalisable beyond participants; limitations include self-selection, varied AI familiarity, uneven institutional policy maturity, potential single-coder bias, and self-defined poll constructs (e.g., "AI literacy").

PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE SURVEY: Mentimeter Results (Appendix 1)

AI LITERACY (N=77)

PROMPT WRITING (N=76)

*AI literacy' and 'prompt writing' were intentionally undefined to prompt discussion; items were retained unchanged across sessions for consistency.

Given capability gaps were a key finding, defining practitioner skill levels may be useful in future institutional initiatives.

USAGE PATTERNS (N=77)

Almost forty per cent of participants who responded to this question said they use “GenAI, (e.g. ChatGPT)” less than daily.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY (N=77)

Over half of respondents to the institutional policy question were either unaware of their institution’s policy or supporting students without one.

OPPORTUNITIES & CHALLENGES

OPPORTUNITIES

Five opportunity themes emerged from the anonymised open-text. They are ordered by salience and illustrated with brief quotes. Appendix 3 lists indicative totals and the method.

1

Student development and skill-building (O1)

Participants recognised opportunities to use AI as a developmental tool for students as the single biggest opportunity. This included helping them “improve their recruiting strategies and marketing materials,” “practice interviews,” “research companies quickly,” and “analyze a resume’s correlation to a job description.” Several stressed that AI should not replace learning, but could act as a “coaching partner and teammate to scale,” supporting critical engagement and reflection. As one participant explained, AI could help students “understand use cases for using it in ways that can help them and be aware of how it can hurt them.”

2

Efficiency and administration (O2)

Another of the most frequently cited opportunities was the ability of AI to streamline routine and repetitive tasks. Participants described how AI could “take out the heavy lifting of admin processes,” provide “quicker resume reviews,” and generate “structured training materials.” These efficiencies would reduce time spent on activities such as resume correction or cover letter feedback, allowing careers educators to redirect their energy toward higher-value work. As one participant put it, AI could “free up time for qualitative tasks such as student guidance” and create “increased bandwidth to serve all student populations.”

3

Personalisation and on-demand access (O3)

Another major opportunity was the provision of personalised and scalable support. Participants described how AI could enable “on-demand, 24/7 and highly tailored” services, offering “unlimited mock interviews and feedback,” “resume reviews, job searches, role matching,” and “diverse resources for different types of learners.” This capacity to deliver consistent, accessible support at scale was viewed as democratising access to career development: “AI levels the playing field” by giving all students the same starting opportunities, regardless of background or location.

4

Innovation and sector intelligence (O4)

AI was also seen as a tool for innovation and exploration. Careers professionals highlighted its role in “job market mapping,” “real-time industry insights,” and “generating company and industry ideas.” It was described as a “great tool for brainstorming” and “career exploration starting points,” with applications ranging from interview preparation to company research. Participants also saw opportunities for careers services themselves to innovate, using AI to “expand knowledge bases,” “co-ordinate with employers,” and “develop new resources.” AI was seen not just a delivery mechanism, but also an engine of creativity and strategic insight.

5

Employer alignment and collaboration (O5)

AI was framed consistently as opening concrete avenues to extend the profession’s remit and impact with employers and students. Participants advocated “formally adding AI as a tool” in day-to-day practice, using it to “stay on top of trends,” “understand AI in workforce planning,” and “explore AI tech and careers.” This would underpin new offerings such as “AI-supported labour-market insights” and deeper external alignment through “co-ordination and collaboration with employers.”

CHALLENGES

Five challenge themes emerged from the anonymised open-text. They are ordered by salience and illustrated with brief quotes. Appendix 3 lists indicative totals and the method.

1

Capability gaps (staff and students) (C1)

Participants acknowledged that both staff and students face significant learning curves in using AI effectively. This was seen as the single biggest challenge. Comments included "poor prompting (everyone looks the same)," "different skill levels," and concerns about "staff proficiency using AI since we are older." Several participants stressed the need for upskilling careers teams and students alike, with one noting the importance of "coaching students to use AI for initial ideas only." The uneven distribution of AI literacy was seen as creating inequities and reducing the effectiveness of services if not addressed through training and support.

2

Authenticity, humanity & learning (C2)

The strongest concerns centred on the risk that AI undermines authenticity and learning. Participants spoke of "lack of authenticity and uniqueness," "uniformity," and the danger that students would rely on "copy and paste rather than critical thinking." Others worried that over-reliance would mean students "never learn how to fish" or "bypass vital skills." A common refrain was the need to ensure students use AI responsibly and recognise its limitations: "How to use it responsibly and ethically. When to seek human counsel. What are its limitations." Without such guidance, career educators see that AI risks eroding the human dimension of career development.

3

Professional identity and relevance (C3)

The risk is role-blur rather than redundancy. Without clear boundaries, AI may be “seen as a competent tool to replace careers advisors,” and students may not “know when to seek human counsel.” The challenge is to codify where automation helps, and where human expertise is essential: “the value of human careers teams providing human skills”. Teams must articulate standards for responsible use, build “AI/human symbiotic skills,” and communicate a clear service model so AI augments rather than eclipses the distinct contribution of careers professionals.

4

Ethics and responsible use (C4)

Ethics emerged as a consistent theme across the discussions. Concerns included “trust in AI companies – data, bias, transparency,” the “rise in dishonesty,” and “made up contents and fake information.” Participants emphasised the importance of “teaching ethical use” and “equipping students for the future, as the use of AI in the workplace is increasing.” There were calls for frameworks, resources, and policies to ensure responsible practice: “Resource for Ethical AI: where, when, how?” Without these, career educators see careers services risk endorsing tools that undermine fairness, authenticity, and employability.

5

Institutional agility and pace (C5)

A further challenge concerned institutional capacity to adapt. Many noted that “AI is fast, academia is slow” and lamented the absence of “a cohesive master plan.” Universities were described as “not agile,” with “risk levels and bureaucracy” slowing innovation. Some participants highlighted a lack of “ownership and accountability” in relation to AI policy, while others noted inconsistency in adoption across departments. The danger, as one participant put it, is that “employees and institutions cannot remain up to date,” leaving careers services without adequate support or direction.

ROLE IMPLICATIONS

The thematic analysis also surfaced five emerging role orientations as professional identity anchors, articulating how business school career consultants envisage their professional practice evolving to best support students.

Professional legitimacy follows from visible employer alignment and transparent, responsible practice rather than from tool adoption alone.

REFLECTIVE QUESTIONS FOR OPPORTUNITIES & CHALLENGES

REFLECTIVE QUESTIONS

These questions are designed to prompt reflection rather than prescribe action. They map to the opportunities and challenges identified in the thematic analysis and can be considered at two levels: how a careers service might respond collectively, and how individual practitioners may adapt their own practice.

OPPORTUNITIES

Theme	Career Service (team/institution)	Individual (your role)
Student development and skill-building	How will we embed AI literacy (technical + critical) into workshops and resources?	How will I coach students to use AI as a learning partner, not a shortcut?
Efficiency and administration	What processes can we redesign so AI delivers repeatable efficiencies across our service?	Where can I use AI to reduce routine work while maintaining quality?
Personalisation, on-demand services and access	How can AI be integrated into our service to extend access and personalisation for students with differing needs and availability?	In what ways might I adapt AI-enabled resources so each student feels the guidance is relevant to their individual context?
Innovation and sectoral intelligence	In what ways might AI strengthen our labour-market data analysis and employer trend mapping?	How might I experiment with AI to expand my own sector knowledge for advising?
Employer alignment and collaboration	With which employers can we form strategic partnerships as a career service?	Who can I reach out to in my employer network to build my knowledge?

CHALLENGES

Theme	Career Service (team/institution)	Individual (your role)
Capability gaps (staff and students)	What training does our team need to use AI competently and equitably?	Which AI skills should I focus on building this year?
Authenticity, humanity and learning	What safeguards can ensure AI supports, rather than replaces, student learning?	What questions can I ask to draw out reflection beyond AI outputs?
Professional identity and relevance	How do we retain trust from students and employers in a digital-first context?	What anchors of professional identity will I rely on in times of change?
Ethics and responsible use	What frameworks and resources do we need to ensure AI use in careers support is ethical, transparent, and aligned with student employability?	How can I model and teach responsible AI use to students?
Institutional agility and pace	How can we create shared ownership and accountability for AI adoption so our policies, resources, and practices keep pace with rapid change?	How do I manage my own confidence when the pace of change feels overwhelming?

CONCLUSION

Across three cohorts, opportunities cluster around student development and efficiency, with innovation and personalisation present at varying strengths; employer alignment is a smaller but consistent theme. Challenges are led by capability gaps, with ethics, institutional agility, authenticity, and professional identity recurrent across cohorts.

For careers educators, the role shifts from information provider to meaning-maker, balancing responsible use with employer-aligned standards, and maintaining the human connection at the core of careers work. Findings reflect a time-bound practitioner snapshot and are intended to stimulate collegial discussion rather than prescribe action.

This report does not prescribe solutions or a single pathway; it offers a starting point and framework for each institution to interpret within its own context. It is intended as a lens for career educators to examine their practice as we enter the age of AI.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1

Mentimeter items, scales & descriptives (totals)

Cohorts included: EMEA conference, Global conference, and a webinar.

Note on constructs: AI literacy and prompt writing were not defined; responses reflect participants' own interpretation.

Question wording & scales (as displayed to participants)

Item (exact wording) and Scale / Options

Q: How would you rate your level of AI literacy overall right now?

O: (None; Basic; Intermediate; Advanced)

Q: Please rate your prompt-writing skill level.

O: (None; Basic; Intermediate; Advanced)

Q: To what extent do you use GenAI (e.g., ChatGPT) in your role?

O: (Never; Monthly; Weekly; Daily; Several times daily; Occasionally)

Q: Does your institution have a policy for the use of AI?

O: (Yes; No; Don't know)

Terminology has been retained as expressed by the participants e.g. "CV" or "resume."

APPENDIX 2

Session prompts and verbatims

Cohorts included: EMEA conference, Global conference, and a webinar

Scope and sources

- EMEA: brainwriting Post-its (Opportunities; Challenges).
- Global: brainwriting Post-its (Opportunities; Challenges).
- Webinar: Mentimeter open-text (where applicable) and word-cloud inputs for the prompt "What words come to mind when you think of AI and Careers Education?" (the integrated visual appears in the main report).

Opportunities prompt (exact wording as displayed at sessions):

- What do you see as the top three opportunities for career services and career educators to use AI in the support of students? (3 Blue **stickies**)

Challenges prompt (exact wording as displayed at sessions):

- What do you see as the top three challenges for career services and career educators to use AI in the support of students? (3 yellow stickies)

Note: A machine-readable file containing the anonymised verbatims can be provided on request.

Terminology has been retained as expressed by the participants e.g. "CV" or "resume."

APPENDIX 3

Opportunities (O1–O5)

Code	Total	Theme heading	Matching A3 entry	Indicative evidence cue
O1	20	Student development and skill-building	Student skill-building & development	"Skills development"; "Structured training materials"; "Coaching partner."
O2	8	Efficiency and administration	Efficiency & admin relief	"Heavy lifting of admin processes"; "Less time on tedious tasks."
O3	8	Personalisation and on-demand access	Personalisation & on-demand access	"On-demand, 24/7 and highly tailored"; "Unlimited mock interviews and feedback."
O4	6	Innovation and sector intelligence	Innovation & sector intelligence	"Job market mapping"; "Real-time industry insights"; "Ideation."
O5	6	Employer alignment and collaboration	Employer alignment & collaboration	"Co-ordinate and collaborate with employers (versus tug-of-war)."

Challenges (C1–C5)

Code	Total Count	Report theme heading	Matching A3 entry	Indicative evidence cue
C1	27	Capability gaps (staff and students)	Capability gaps & prompting skills	"Prompt engineering expertise"; "Team upskilling needed."
C2	12	Authenticity, humanity and learning	Student learning risks & over-reliance/homogenisation	"Copy and paste rather than critical thinking"; "Sameness; uniformity."
C3	10	Professional identity and relevance	Professional identity & relevance	"Fear of reduced career centre relevancy/need."
C4	7	Ethics and responsible use	Ethics, bias & privacy	"Bias, transparency"; "Privacy and compliance"; "Trust in AI companies."
C5	5	Institutional agility and pace	Pace & institutional agility/governance	"AI is fast, academia is slow"; "No ownership and accountability."

Counts aggregate EMEA, Global and Webinar open-text; one count per note per theme (keyword scan). Estimates are indicative and do not replace full qualitative coding.

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